

THE USE OF SOCIAL MEDIA AND ITS IMPACT TO ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN ENGLISH AMONG SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS AT SULU COLLEGE OF TECHNOLOGY, INC.

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ABSTRACT

Using 100 samples obtained through the non-probability sampling method via purposive sampling, this descriptive-correlational study evaluated the use of social media and its impact to academic performance in English among senior high school students at Sulu College of Technology, Incorporated during the School Year 2023–2024. Using the weighted mean, standard deviation, t-test for independent samples, one-way ANOVA, and Pearson's r , the study revealed the following findings: Overall, senior high school students used social media moderately in relation to their academic performance in English; In general, factors such as age, gender, and grade level did not significantly mediate in ways how senior high school students assessed the use of social media in relation to their academic performance in English; Of the 100 student-respondents, the majority were female and between the ages of 17 and under; The group of senior high school students from Sulu College of Technology, Inc. who evaluated the impact of social media use on academic performance in English by measuring the amount of time spent on social media as moderately extensive was likely the same group of students who evaluated the impact on English grades and the extent of academic engagement on social media, respectively. This study appeared to validate the idea put forth by Hoffman and Novak (2012) that people use social media in the context of their basic needs for autonomy, competence, and relatedness, as well as their intrinsic and external motivations and perceptions of their well-being.

Keywords: *Social media, Academic performance, Sulu College of Technology Inc., Philippines*

INTRODUCTION

In the current era, it is essentially important to be aware of various things that could have an impact on one's life on all levels—mentally, emotionally, and physically. There are situations when it is definitely necessary to investigate various social media sites that can have an effect on day-to-day living.

Social media has become an almost necessary element of daily life in today's culture, especially for university students who use it extensively. There are numerous social media platforms that undoubtedly become a part of daily life (Lau, 2017).

Social media platforms like Facebook, YouTube, Twitter, and others have expanded astronomically in the last 10 years, gaining an enormous user base. Social media has unavoidably become a crucial component of modern education, the public relations and advertising sectors, political campaigns, and many other facets of our everyday lives (Lexington, 2011).

Universities, colleges, and schools are now exposed to a variety of platforms that help students grow and enhance their surroundings. For these institutions, students are the most valuable resource. There is a clear correlation between student achievement and social media use. Academic excellence of the students is crucial in developing the highest calibre graduates who will serve as outstanding leaders and sources of labour for the nation. Paul et al. (2012) noted that time spent on online social networks has a statistically significant negative relationship with students' academic performance, influenced by their attention span. Social media use has a positive influence on students' perceptions of their academic performance in higher education (Al-Adwan, 2020).

METHODOLOGY

The research study was carried out in a private institution in Jolo, Sulu. Survey questionnaires were the primary tool used in the study's descriptive exploratory research design to collect the necessary data. In this investigation, a purposive sample process was used as a none-probability sampling method. The study had one hundred (100) respondents in total as participants. While collecting the descriptive and correlational data, the Sulu State College Graduate Studies Dean was consulted for permission to proceed with the study. The researcher applied for and received permission to perform the study from the school administration, and once that was done, the researcher provided the approved permission to do so.

Research Objectives

The objectives of the study were:

1. To determine the demographic profile of the Senior High School Students.
2. To determine the extent of the impact of the use social media in the academic performance in English among Senior High School Students.
3. To determine the significant difference in the extent of the impact of the use of social media on Academic Performance in English among Senior High School Students.
4. To determine the significant correlation among the sub-categories subsume under the impact of the use of social media on academic performance in English among senior high school students.

RESULTS

Demographic Profile

The age distribution of the senior high school student responders is shown in Table 1.1. This table shows that, of the 100 student respondents, 45 (45.0%) are between the ages of 17 and under, 42 (42.0%) are between the ages of 18 and 19, and 13 (13.0%) are between the ages of 20 and over. According to this study, around 50% of Sulu College of Technology, Inc.'s senior high school students for the 2023–2024 academic year are between the ages of 17 and under, with those between the ages of 18 and 19 coming in second and third, respectively.

Table 1.1 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in Terms of Age

Age	Number of Students	Percent
17 years old & below	45	45.0%
18-190 years old	42	42.0%
20 years old & above	13	13.0%
Total	100	100%

The gender demographic profile of the senior high school student respondents is displayed in Table 1.2. This table indicates that, of the 100 student responders, 22 (22.0%) are men and 78 (78.0%) are women. our indicates that a far greater proportion of female students than male students—more than three-fourths of the vast majority of student respondents in our study—are female. According to this outcome, for the academic year 2023–2024, female senior high school students will predominate over their male counterparts in terms of enrollment.

Table 1.2 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in Terms of Gender

Gender	Number of Students	Percent
Male	22	22.0%
Female	78	78.0%
Total	100	100%

The year-by-year breakdown of the senior high school student respondents is provided in Table 1.3. This table indicates that 39 (39.0%) of the 100 student responses are enrolled in Grade 11, and 61 (61.0%) are enrolled in Grade 12. According to this survey, Grade 12 students for the School Year 2023–2024 comprise approximately three-fourths, or the vast majority, of the senior high school students at Sulu College of Technology, Inc.

Table 1.3 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in Terms of Grade Level

Grade Level	Number of Students	Percent
Grade 11	39	39.0%
Grade 12	61	61.0%
Total	100	100%

On Time Spent on Social Media

The extent to which social media use affects senior high school students at Sulu College of Technology, Inc.'s academic performance in English is demonstrated in Table 2.1 by means of the amount of time spent on social media. The overall weighted mean score of the students' assessment falls into this category at 3.7150, with a standard deviation of .58247, so it is classified as Moderate Extent. This finding suggests that the study's student respondents begged to use social media in a moderate way.

Specifically, among the items in this area, student respondents gave the following explicit ratings of Moderate Extent: "How much time do you usually spend on social media?" "Do you utilise social media for studying purposes?" "When studying, do you check your social media accounts?" "Do you think using social media interferes with the time I spend studying English?" "Has the amount of time you spend on social media changed since you started senior high school?" "Does social media cause you to become sidetracked from your English studies?", and "Does social media induce you to stay up late?".

Table 2.1 Extent of the Impact of Social Media Use on Students' Academic Performance in English among the Students in terms of Time Spent on Social Media

	Statements	Mean	S.D.	Rating
1.	Do you typically spend on social media?	3.9300	1.01757	Moderate Extent
2.	Do you use social media during your study time?	3.7400	.97047	Moderate Extent
3.	Do you check your Social Media accounts while studying?	3.6100	1.11821	Moderate Extent
4.	Do you think your social media usage affects my English study time?	3.7000	1.07778	Moderate Extent
5.	Has your time on social media has increased or decreased since starting Senior High School?	3.6300	1.22808	Moderate Extent
6.	Do you feel distracted from your English Studies due to social media?	3.7000	1.12367	Moderate Extent
7.	Do you stay up late because of social media?	3.7500	.85723	Moderate Extent
8.	Has social media ever caused you to miss English assignments or deadlines?	3.7400	.96001	Moderate Extent
9.	Do you think reducing social media improves your English Academic Performance?	3.6500	1.01876	Moderate Extent
10.	Do you use strategies to balance social media and your English studies?	3.7000	.98985	Moderate Extent
Total Weighted Mean		3.7150	.58247	Moderate Extent

Legend: (5) 4.50-5.0=Great Extent (GE); (4) 3.50 – 4.49= Moderate Extent (ME); (3) 2.50 – 3.49= Lesser Extent (LE); (2) 1.50 – 2.49=Least Extent (LtE); (1) 1.00 – 1.49=No Extent (NE)

On Academic Engagement on Social Media

Table 2.2 illustrates the degree to which academic involvement on social media among senior high school students at Sulu College of Technology, Inc. is impacted by their use of social media. The overall weighted mean score of the students' assessment falls into this category at 3.6420 with a standard deviation of .61351, so it is classified as Moderate Extent. This finding suggests that the study's student respondents begged to participate in English-related social media debates in a moderate way.

Students who responded to this category explicitly ranked the following items as Moderate Extent: "Are you a member of English-related organisations or forums on Social Media?" "Do you engage in conversations about English on social media?" "Have you used social media to look for guidance on English concepts or assignments?" "Do you follow social media accounts or pages dedicated to learning English language skills?" "Has interacting with English-language information on social media enhanced your academic achievement?" "Have you ever used social media to get helpful criticism on your English writing?" and "To what extent do you feel at ease utilising social media for academic English-related purposes?".

Table 2.2 Extent of the Impact of Social Media Use on Students' Academic Performance in English among the Students in terms of Time Spent on Academic Engagement on Social Media

	Statements	Mean	S.D.	Rating
1.	Are you a member of English-related groups or forums on social media?	3.0900	1.29564	Lesser Extent
2.	Do you participate in English-related discussions on social media?	3.6300	.88369	Moderate Extent
3.	Have you used social media to seek help with English assignments or concepts?	3.5000	.91563	Moderate Extent
4.	Do you follow English Language learning pages or accounts on social media?	3.7800	1.09710	Moderate Extent
5.	Has engaging with English content on social media improved your academic performance?	3.6500	1.14040	Moderate Extent
6.	Have you ever received constructive feedback on your English work through social media?	3.6700	1.08297	Moderate Extent
7.	How comfortable are you using social media for English-related for academic purposes?	3.8100	.98160	Moderate Extent
8.	Do you believe social media can enhance your English language skills?	3.8500	1.05768	Moderate Extent
9.	Has social media ever distracted you from your academic responsibilities?	3.6200	1.08971	Moderate Extent
10.	Would you recommend using social media for English learning to your peers?	3.8200	.89194	Moderate Extent
	Total Weighted Mean	3.6420	.61351	Moderate Extent

Legend: (5) 4.50-5.0=Great Extent (GE); (4) 3.50 – 4.49= Moderate Extent (ME); (3) 2.50 – 3.49= Lesser Extent (LE); (2) 1.50 – 2.49=Least Extent (Lt.E); (1) 1.00 – 1.49=No Extent (NE)

On Impact on English Grades

The amount to which social media use affects senior high school students at Sulu College of Technology, Inc.'s English academic performance in terms of impact on English grades is displayed in Table 2.3. The overall weighted mean score of the students' assessment falls into this category at 3.6730, with a standard deviation of .55320, so it is classified as Moderate Extent. This finding suggests that the study's student respondents believed social media use had a minor impact on their academic achievement in English.

Students who responded to this category explicitly ranked the following items as Moderate Extent: "Have your English grades improved or deteriorated while utilizing social media regularly? "Do you think using social media has improved your English scores? "Have you ever used social media to get academic help or English resources? "Do you believe using social media has improved or worsened your ability to concentrate on English homework? "Have you ever allowed social media to divert your attention from your English exam preparation? "How frequently do you look for information on social networking sites for English assignments?", and "Have you ever worked with students on English assignments using social media?"

Table 2.3 Extent of the Impact of Social Media Use on Students' Academic Performance in English among the Students in terms of Impact on English Grades

Statements		Mean	S.D.	Rating
1.	How would you rate your current English academic performance (e.g., your grades)?	3.5000	.92660	Lesser Extent
2.	Have your English grades improved or declined since using social media regularly?	3.6400	.75905	Moderate Extent
3.	Do you believe that social media has positively affected your English grades?	3.7800	.90543	Moderate Extent
4.	Have you ever received academic support or resources to English through social media?	3.6200	1.08040	Moderate Extent
5.	Do you think social media has made it easier or harder to focus on English assignments?	3.5800	.93398	Moderate Extent
6.	Have you ever been distracted by social media when studying for English exams?	3.6200	.96169	Moderate Extent
7.	How often do you use social media as a reference for English assignments?	3.6000	1.01504	Moderate Extent
8.	Have you ever used social media to collaborate with classmates on English projects?	3.5900	.99590	Moderate Extent
9.	Do you think English grades would be better without social media?	3.9100	1.00599	Moderate Extent
10.	How would you describe the overall impact of social media on your English academic performance?	3.8900	1.13614	Moderate Extent
Total Weighted Mean		3.6730	.55320	Moderate Extent

Legend: (5) 4.50-5.0=Great Extent (GE); (4) 3.50 – 4.49= Moderate Extent (ME); (3) 2.50 – 3.49= Lesser Extent (LE); (2) 1.50 – 2.49=Least Extent (Lt.E); (1) 1.00 – 1.49=No Extent (NE)

On the significant difference of the extent of the impact of the use of social media to academic performance in English according to age, gender and grade level

Table 3.1 presents the differences in the extent of the impact of the use of social media on academic performance in English among senior high school students at Sulu College of Technology, Inc. when data are categorized according to their demographic profile in terms of age. It can be gleaned from this table that the values of F-ratios and *P*-values of all the sub-categories subsumed under the impact of the use of social media on academic performance in English among senior high school students are not significant at alpha .05. This means that although student-respondents vary in age range, yet they do not differ in their perceptions towards the impact of the use of social media on academic performance in English among senior high school students. This result implies that being older or within 20 years old & above may not necessarily put a student-respondent in vantage point towards perceiving the impact of the use of social media on academic performance in English among senior high school students than those who are within 17 years old & below as well as those within 18-19 years old, or vice versa.

Nonetheless, it is safe to say that variable age has no significant mediation in ways how student-respondents assess the impact of the use of social media on academic performance in English among senior high school students. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that “There is no significant difference in the extent of the impact of the use of Social Media on Academic Performance in English among Senior High School Students at Sulu College of Technology, Inc. in terms of age” is accepted.

Table 3.1 Demographic profile in terms of age

SOURCES OF VARIATION		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Time Spent on Social Media	Between Groups	1.035	2	.518	1.542	.219	Not Significant
	Within Groups	32.552	97	.336			
	Total	33.588	99				
Academic Engagement on Social Media	Between Groups	.165	2	.083	.216	.806	Not Significant
	Within Groups	37.098	97	.382			
	Total	37.264	99				
Impact on English Grades	Between Groups	.440	2	.220	.715	.492	Not Significant
	Within Groups	29.857	97	.308			
	Total	30.297	99				

*Significant alpha .05

Table 3.2 shows the differences in the extent of the impact of the use of social media on academic performance in English among senior high school students at Sulu College of Technology, Inc. when data are categorized according to their demographic profile in terms of gender. It can be gleaned from this table that the values of mean differences of all the sub-categories subsumed under the impact of the use of social media on academic performance in English among senior high school students are not significant at alpha .05. This means that male and female student-respondents do not differ in their perceptions towards the impact of the use of social media on academic performance in English among senior high school students. This finding implies that being a male student may not necessarily put him in a vantage point towards perceiving the impact of the use of social media on academic performance in English among senior high school students than his female counterpart, or vice versa.

Consequently, it is safe to say that variable gender has no significant influence in the ways how student-respondents assess the impact of the use of social media on academic performance in English among senior high school students. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that “There is no significant difference in the extent of the impact of the use of social media on academic performance in English among senior high school students at Sulu College of Technology, Inc. in terms of gender” is accepted.

Table 3.2 Demographic profile in terms of gender

VARIABLES Grouping		Mean	S. D.	Mean Difference	t	Sig.	Description
Time Spent on Social Media	Male	3.7409	.54568	.03322	.235	.815	Not Significant
	Female	3.7077	.59560				
Academic Engagement on Social Media	Male	3.5136	.78516	-.16457	-1.113	.269	Not Significant
	Female	3.6782	.55658				
Impact on English Grades	Male	3.6455	.61623	-.03531	-.263	.793	Not Significant
	Female	3.6808	.53817				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

Table 3.3 shows the differences in the extent of the impact of the use of social media on academic performance in English among senior high school students at Sulu College of Technology, Inc. when data are categorized according to their demographic profile in terms of grade level. It can be gleaned from this table that, except for “Time Spent on Social Media” the values of mean differences of all other sub-categories subsumed under the impact of the use of social media on academic performance in English among senior high school students are not significant at alpha .05. This means that although student-respondents enrolled in different grade levels, yet do not differ in their perceptions towards the impact of the use of social media on academic performance in English among senior high school students. This finding implies that a student-respondent enrolled as Grade 12 may not necessarily put him in a vantage point towards perceiving the impact of the use of social media on academic performance in English among senior high school students than those enrolled as Grade 11, or vice versa.

Consequently, it is safe to say that variable grade level has no significant influence in the ways how student-respondents assess the impact of the use of social media on academic performance in English among senior high school students. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that “There is no significant difference in the extent of the impact of the use of Social Media on Academic Performance in English among Senior High School Students at Sulu College of Technology, Inc. in terms of grade level” is accepted.

Table 3.3 Demographic profile in terms of grade level

VARIABLES Grouping		Mean	S. D.	Mean Difference	t	Sig.	Description
Time Spent on Social Media	Male	3.8641	.44691	.24443*	2.081	.040	Significant
	Female	3.6197	.64001				
Academic Engagement on Social Media	Male	3.7308	.63791	.14552	1.159	.249	Not Significant
	Female	3.5852	.59577				
Impact on English Grades	Male	3.8000	.50158	.20820	1.858	.066	Not Significant
	Female	3.5918	.57309				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

On the significant correlation among the sub-categorized subsume under the impact of the use of Social Media on Academic Performance in English among Senior High School Students at Sulu College of Technology, Inc.

The link between the sub-categories under the heading "Impact of Social Media Use on Academic Performance in English Among Senior High School Students at Sulu College of Technology, Inc." is shown in Table 4. This table indicates that there is substantial Pearson Correlation Coefficients (Pearson r) between these variables at alpha.05.

As of right now, it is reasonable to conclude that there is a strong correlation between the number of subcategories that fall under the umbrella of the effect of social media use on academic performance in English among senior high school students at Sulu College of Technology, Inc.

Consequently, the hypothesis that claims, "Among senior high school students at Sulu College of Technology, Inc., there is no significant correlation among the sub-categories subsume under the impact of the use of Social Media on Academic Performance in English." is rejected.

Table 4 Correlation among the Sub-Categorized Subsume under the Impact of the use of Social Media on academic performance in English among Senior High School Students at Sulu College of Technology, Inc.

Variables		Pearson r	Sig	N	Description
Dependent	Independent				
Time Spent on Social Media	Academic Engagement on Social Media	.662**	.000	100	High
	Impact on English Grades	.654**	.000	100	High

*Correlation Coefficient is significant at alpha .05

Correlation Coefficient Scales Adopted from Hopkins, Will (2002):

0.0-0.1=Nearly Zero; 0.1-0.30=Low; .3-0.5 0=Moderate; .5-0.7-0=High; .7-0.9= Very High; 0.9-1=Nearly Perfect

DISCUSSION

On Demographic Profile Student-Respondents

According to this study, around 50% of Sulu College of Technology, Inc.'s senior high school students for the 2023–2024 academic year are between the ages of 17 and under, with those between the ages of 18 and 19 coming in second and third, respectively. There are significantly more female students than male students among the student responders, making up three-fourths of the total. For the School Year 2023–2024, Grade 12 represents approximately three-fourths, or the vast majority, of the senior high school students at Sulu College of Technology, Inc.

On the extent of the impact of the use social media in the academic performance in English among senior high school students

The study's results indicate that the amount of time spent on social media is moderate. Social Media Academic Engagement is ranked as Moderate Extent. The degree of the impact on English grades is graded as moderate.

On the Differences in the extent of the impact of the use of social media on Academic Performance in English among Senior High School Students

When data are categorized based on the age demographic profile of the senior high school students at Sulu College of Technology, Inc., there is no discernible variation in the effect of social media use on Academic Performance in English.

When data are categorised based on the gender demographic profile of senior high school students at Sulu College of Technology, Inc., there is no discernible variation in the influence of social media use on academic performance in English.

When data are categorized based on the demographic profile of senior high school students at Sulu College of Technology, Inc., there is no discernible variation in the effect of social media use on academic performance in English.

On the Correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under the use of social media on Academic Performance in English among Senior High School Students

In terms of time spent on social media, academic engagement on social media, and impact on English grades, there is in fact a strong positive correlation between the subcategories included under the use of social media on Academic Performance in English among Senior High School Students at Sulu College of Technology, Inc.

Conclusions

This study concluded the following based of the findings above:

1)The study's sample of senior high school students is adequately representative in terms of age, gender, and grade level.

2) Senior high school students used social media somewhat on average, which had an impact on their English academic performance.

3)Generally speaking, senior high school students' assessments of the impact of social media use on their academic performance in English are not significantly mediated by factors such as age, gender, or grade level.

4) In general, the senior high school students at Sulu College of Technology, Inc. who evaluated the influence of social media use on academic performance in English by assessing the time spent on social media as moderate extent are most likely the same students who evaluated the impact on English grades and the degree of academic engagement on social media, respectively.

5) The idea put forth by Donna L. Hoffman and Thomas Novak (2012) that emphasises how people utilise social media in relation to their fundamental requirements for autonomy, competence, and relatedness as well as their internal and external motives and perceptions of their well-being appears to be supported by this study.

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